

CERTAIN ASPECTS OF THE CRITERIA AND PRINCIPLES OF ECOLOGICAL CULTURE IN THE LIFE OF SOCIETY

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14543553>

Azamat Mukhtorov

Doctor of Philosophy, Professor, TSUE

Vahob Kuchkarov

Doctor of Political Sciences, Professor, TSUE

Email: abduvahob.uz@mail.ru

Abstract: *The present article investigates the criteria and principles for enhancing ecological culture in society, focusing on the theoretical foundations and practical applications of this process. The research highlights the importance of education, technological innovations, and active public participation in promoting environmental awareness. The study analyzes Uzbekistan's experience with ecological initiatives, including state programs such as the "Green Space" project, and compares them with successful global practices in countries like Sweden, Germany, and Japan. Recommendations include integrating ecological culture into education systems, fostering public engagement, and supporting innovative technologies for sustainability. The findings aim to contribute to achieving sustainable development goals (SDGs) by integrating ecological culture into societal structures.*

Keywords: *ecological culture, sustainable development, criteria, principles, education, technological innovations, public participation, Uzbekistan, global practices.*

INTRODUCTION

In the management of the state and society and in ensuring the continuity of human life, the surrounding environment, the environment in which it lives, and the issue of ensuring its viability and cleanliness are more important and urgent than ever. In this sense, today, the formation of an ecological culture, especially paying attention to environmental education and increasing ecological culture among various segments of the population, is a requirement of the times. The main reason for this is that the air we breathe, the water we drink, and the products we eat are becoming increasingly polluted every day and hour. It is especially worth noting that the air quality in Tashkent has reached record levels in recent years, which is certainly related to the processes of globalization and urbanization taking place in the world. In Uzbekistan, large-scale work is also being carried out in this regard at the

government level. In particular, the implementation of the national project "Green Space" every year at the initiative of the head of our state is a confirmation of this. The Action Plan, approved by the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-300 dated September 11, 2023 on measures for the qualitative and timely implementation of the "Uzbekistan - 2030" Strategy in 2023, sets out important tasks: "Expanding the national project "Green Space" aimed at stabilizing the ecological situation, expanding the area of forests, stabilizing the ecological situation in the Aral Sea region, mitigating the negative impact of environmental problems resulting from the drying up of the Aral Sea, preventing the negative impact of climate change, preventing air pollution, and taking drastic measures to preserve its natural composition" [1.36]. Therefore, environmental problems remain one of the most pressing issues in modern society. Threats such as global warming, resource depletion, and environmental pollution require increased attention of humanity to ecological culture. In particular, the lack of ecological culture is leading to the deepening of many problems. These problems negatively affect not only nature, but also the economic, social and cultural development of society.

This issue is also extremely important for Uzbekistan. In Central Asia, environmental problems, including the drying up of the Aral Sea, soil erosion, and the lack of water resources, are limiting the sustainable development of the country. In these conditions, the development of ecological culture and its transformation into an integral part of public life are considered an urgent issue.

So, the problem is clear. The main problem is the implementation of a number of tasks in this area in the life of society, both theoretically and practically. It should be noted that the pragmatic aspect of the problem is certainly related to the activities of responsible persons, state and non-governmental organizations.

Theoretically, it requires a scientific approach to the problem, along with propaganda and awareness-raising work among all strata of society, including the population and youth. Thus, it is appropriate to highlight the views on ecological culture, its components, as well as criteria and elements. Therefore, the main purpose of this article is to highlight the scientific and practical foundations of increasing ecological culture in public life. The research will analyze the criteria and principles necessary to increase environmental culture, as well as study national and international experiences in this process.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

In this article, an attempt was made to use a number of scientific methods, such as systematic analysis, social survey, content analysis, and historicism, to illuminate the criteria and principles of forming an ecological culture in the life of society. In

particular, the following research methods are used in the article to analyze the problems associated with increasing ecological culture:

- Historical-analytical approach: analysis of the development of the concept of ecological culture.
- Analysis of empirical data: study of statistical data on the development of ecological culture in Uzbekistan and other countries.
- Comparative analysis: adaptation of the experiences of countries of the world to the conditions of Uzbekistan.

The article highlights the theoretical and practical aspects of the formation and development of an ecological culture, and identifies the main principles that contribute to the success of this process. At the same time, a number of literature was studied within the framework of the topic. In particular, works studied in neighboring foreign countries are cited. In particular, Russian scientists describe environmental problems on a smaller discursive scale of behavior. Russian scholars often deal with the topic of environmental action in a meaningful way, within the framework of research in the field of ecological culture[2012.41], the phenomenon of environmental practices[2011.226], as well as a systematic approach to analyzing various dimensions of conscious environmental action. It is also important to note that the components of the problem of environmental action in local works are authors within the framework of the concepts of sustainable development[2012.318] and socio-ecological modernization. Studies related to sociological reflection on the problems of formation and development have been conducted.

Naturally, local scientists have also conducted a number of studies on this issue. Of these, the role and content of ecological culture in the life of society have been studied theoretically and practically by the researcher K. Sh.Karabukaev[2018.230]. In the work of the Uzbek scientist Z. Sh.Yazdonova's[2019.11] PhD thesis examined the traditions of the ecological culture of the Uzbek people, the moral principles that are included in its historical heritage. And again, from the field work, an Explanatory dictionary of basic terms and phrases related to ecology, compiled by A.I.Nigmatov[2002.15], should be given.

DISCUSSION

As is known, many views and definitions have been given to the concepts of ecology and ecological culture. They mainly state that “Ecology does not mean keeping the streets clean, protecting water, and protecting the air from pollution.

Ecology is an independent science that studies life processes and human environmental problems in its own unique ways. The methodological basis of modern ecology is a systematic approach, observations in nature, experimentation, and modeling. Ecology is both a natural and social (humanitarian) science [2006.13]”.

Indeed, the formation of ecological culture is the first priority in eliminating and preventing many problems related to ecology and the environment. In recent years, many reforms have been carried out in the family, neighborhood, and ecological spheres, and new directions and structures have emerged.

Consequently, ecological culture is an integral part of universal human culture, which includes a system of social relations, moral values, norms and methods of interaction of society with the natural environment, and is gradually formed in social consciousness and behavior throughout the life and activities of people. Through continuous environmental education and enlightenment, it is possible to contribute to a healthy lifestyle for generations, the spiritual growth of society, sustainable socio-economic development of the country and the environmental safety of each person. Therefore, it can be said that ecological culture is a process of vital activity, norms and values of society, which are associated with the attitude towards the environment. It is worth emphasizing that in the process of globalization, the struggle of humanity for survival is becoming increasingly evident, and today it is clear that special attention is paid to ecological culture. Indeed, by changing a person's worldview, values, and his attitude to ordinary everyday things, it is possible to change his attitude towards the environment.

The ecological culture of society is a system of dialectically interconnected elements: ecological relations, ecological consciousness and ecological activity. The content of ecological relations includes two structural elements: socio-ecological relations that develop between people in an artificial living environment and indirectly affect the natural living environment of people, and, firstly, the direct relationship of man to the natural environment, secondly, the relationship associated with the process of human assimilation of natural forces, energy and matter in the material and production spheres of human life, and thirdly, real-practical relations, which include human relations. While, the ecological consciousness - consciousness towards the environment - encompasses our ideas, behavior, sphere of activity, desires and hopes related to the natural environment. Having ecological consciousness means being aware of the limitations of nature, of which man is an integral part; the need to abandon human domination over nature and the need to establish a dynamic balance between natural systems and society; the global nature of the environmental crisis and the need to solve it; the need for a global development strategy as a necessary condition for the existence of life. Therefore, to overcome environmental problems, society must solve an important task - the formation of environmental consciousness among the population. It includes the entire complex of environmental education and upbringing in order to establish such elements as ecological scientific consciousness, environmental ethics, psychology and legal

consciousness as dominant in social consciousness. Ecological scientific consciousness involves the formation of a scientific picture of the world based on the achievements of modern science.

In particular, a systemic approach, taking into account the world in its interaction and integrity, comes to the fore; the principle of universal evolutionism, as well as modern concepts and theories such as synergism, Vernadsky's theory of the biosphere and noosphere, T. de Chardin's doctrine of the human phenomenon. It is precisely the scientific ecological consciousness that should be the basis for environmental policy and practice. In the formation of ecological consciousness, an important role is played by ecological ethics based on ecological humanism, a sense of personal responsibility for the state of the natural environment, which arises with an increase in the moral level of man.

Ecological psychology is also an important component of ecological consciousness. Its essence can be briefly expressed as follows: love for nature, for all living things as a character trait, or, as E. Fromm said, the essence of ecological psychology is biophilia, which means "the desire to support growth and development." "Ecological awareness should also be included in the ecological consciousness, which means the understanding of the legal responsibility of all citizens for harming nature and the legal protection of the latter. And this, of course, should be constantly confirmed by effective legal measures. The main features or signs of ecological consciousness are: the social nature of ecological consciousness, which is associated with the norms, values and traditions accepted in society; mediation by symbols, signs, including verbal means of human perception of the natural world; self-reflexivity; internal dialogism, etc. There are such types of ecological consciousness as anthropocentric and ecocentric. Signs of anthropocentric ecological consciousness: The highest value is expressed by man; hierarchical picture of the world; the purpose of interaction with nature is to satisfy certain pragmatic needs; When approached from a philosophical point of view "Pragmatic imperative": what is right is what is beneficial to man; nature is accepted as an object of human activity; moral norms and rules do not apply to interactions with the natural world; the development of nature is viewed as a process that must be subordinate to human goals and objectives; nature conservation activities are characterized by long-term pragmatism: the need to preserve the natural environment so that future generations can use it.

Ecocentric ecological consciousness is a special form of reflection of natural objects and phenomena of reality and their interrelationships, which determines the goal-setting and transforming activity of man, characterized by providing nature with subjective characteristics, as a result of which nature itself is recognized as a value,

relations with it are based on the specific characteristics of man. The principles of equality due to the predominance of non-pragmatic motivation and the spread of moral norms to the natural world and rules. Characteristics of ecocentric ecological consciousness: The harmonious development of man and nature is the highest value; rejection of a hierarchical worldview; The goal of relations with nature is to optimally satisfy both human needs and the needs of the entire natural society; "ecological imperative": it is right not to violate the ecological balance existing in nature; nature is perceived as an equal subject from the point of view of relations with people; ethical norms and rules apply equally to human interaction and interaction with nature; The development of nature is viewed as a process of mutually beneficial unity; Nature protection activities are determined by the need to preserve nature for itself and for people. Ecological activity is characterized as an integral concept that encompasses various types of human activity in the material and ideal spheres related to the knowledge, development, transformation and preservation of the natural environment.

The concept of "ecological activity" encompasses various types of human activity, considered in a certain way in various levels of material, practical and theoretical spheres related to the study, development, transformation and preservation of the natural environment. Thus, on the one hand, it is the broadest sphere of human activity, and on the other hand, it is the sphere that is the basis of the initial, primary support of human life. It is clear that man has been engaged in environmental activity since his appearance on Earth. It has been consistently transformed in accordance with the stages of development of environmental culture in general, and therefore at present it must correspond to a new type of environmental culture and all its subsystems, primarily to the modern level of environmental thinking. From a practical point of view, environmental activity is a productive activity of a person with transformational and ecological goals, that is, environmental management.

When studying and systematizing environmental problems, a philosophical approach to the problem requires viewing it in connection with the life of environmental culture, the state and society, broad segments of the population, and students. In this sense, ecological culture is a set of knowledge, values, and skills that reflect the responsible attitude of the individual and society to nature. This concept implies the active participation of a person in protecting the environment, rational use of natural resources, and responding to environmental problems. Many scientists around the world, discussing ecological culture, have proposed various interpretations of this concept:

• Aldo Leopold (1949) in his work "A Sand County Almanac" calls ecological ethics "earth ethics" and emphasizes the values that ensure human life in harmony with nature.

• UNESCO (2017) defines ecological culture as a key part of global citizenship, which requires every person to be attentive to environmental problems and to respond responsibly.

• The importance of preserving the purity of nature, paying attention to the purity of soil and water is also reflected in the ancient Avesta Scriptures. According to them, the purity of water and air is a prerequisite for labor and leisure. The concept of ecological culture in Uzbekistan was developed based on national traditions. Historical figures such as Alisher Navoi and Babur emphasized the need to appreciate and preserve nature in their works. Today, this tradition is reflected in modern environmental policy and social life.

Today, the negative consequences of global environmental changes are reflected in the fact that countries, striving for economic and political dominance and gaining great prestige, are placing special emphasis on national production, which is causing a global environmental crisis. On the other hand, people themselves are also responsible for the wasteful use of nature. Compared to the last century, the way of life of humanity has changed so much that it is clear to all of us that global warming, which has never been observed in human civilization, an unprecedented decrease in marine and terrestrial ecosystems, and a number of negative situations such as droughts and floods are occurring in various regions of the world. In short, human interference with nature has reached an unthinkable level. Well, we have problems, but what about solutions to them? Is it possible that no one is even remotely interested in the global environmental situation in the world today? What kind of future are we leaving to the next generation? How long will such painful questions torment us every time? Is it possible that the current state of the world is getting worse day by day, and we, as humans, will continue to look at it as if it were just a normal phenomenon? What if the leaders of countries, government representatives, and all of humanity are interested in nothing more than increasing wealth, economic growth, political dominance, and gaining great prestige among countries?! Yes, of course, we are used to it and have been living with it!

As a result of the development of human civilization and its ever-deepening penetration into the bosom of nature, the situation has changed radically. Today, it is impossible to talk about the pristine nature. Because the forests on Earth have been cut down, vast territories have been developed for farming, fertilized with pesticides, and the fresh air and nature have been polluted with various wastes and gases. In addition, floods, forest fires, dust storms, and other natural processes occur in nature.

All of this disrupts the natural balance of nature. Natural, anthropogenic, or purely anthropogenic phenomena observed around the world are considered universal problems. Let us give some examples of such environmental problems:

1. The phenomenon of “atmospheric pollution”.
2. The phenomenon of “ozone layer depletion”.
3. The problem of “fresh water”.
4. The problem of "decline in the number of plant and animal species in living nature".

5. The problem of "use of pesticides". Regional environmental problems. A certain region of the Earth's surface has its own natural climate, socio-ecological, ethnographic features that determine the nature of the interaction between nature and man. Human development, the acceleration of urbanization, and the acceleration of globalization have undermined the security of our Mother Planet, creating a number of issues, including environmental problems. The ecological threat that is causing serious damage to the environment, when it comes, is even more terrible than nuclear disaster and terrorism, and is forcing all peoples of the Earth to think more deeply about it. According to a joint study by the World Wildlife Fund (WWF), the Global Footprint Network, and the Zoological Society of London, since 1970, the number of wild animals and birds on Earth has decreased by 3,430 species, and the Living Planet Index has decreased by 52%, that is, the number of species living in the air and on land has decreased by 76%, and the number of species living on land and in water has decreased by 39%. Every year, 11 million hectares of tropical forests are cut down and destroyed due to human activity. This is 10 times more than the work on reforestation. Every day, about 60 million tons of carbon dioxide are released into the atmosphere, which leads to warming of the air and, in turn, to a rise in the water level of the World Ocean [2020].

Have you ever heard of Mina Guli or read about her? Or do you know the woman who walked through seven deserts in search of water?! If you haven't read or heard about her, you probably don't care that the world's population is dying from lack of water! What if I told you that in 15 years you will die from lack of water?! "Many people are unaware that we are running out of fresh water, and by 2030 there will be a 40% gap between demand and supply. We have only 15 years to solve the water problem," says Mina Guli, the Young Global Leader of the World Economic Forum. It is worth noting that a survey conducted by a team of 750 experts assessed the depletion of clean drinking water as a truly global threat to the entire world's population. In fact, the problem of drinking water has already taken its place at the forefront of the problems that plague the world's population. It is not easy for those

who do not have enough water to use, and spend their days searching for clean drinking water! How can those who waste water know these feelings!

RESULTS

The main principles of environmental education are: universality; complexity; continuity; distribution of interdisciplinary connections; the relationship between global, national and local history; the principle of revealing environmental problems and pragmatism. mass media and communication. Principles of organizing environmental education and upbringing:

1. The process of forming a responsible attitude to nature is an integral part of the general education system, its current direction.

2. The process of forming an ecological culture is based on the interrelation of global, regional and local approaches to revealing modern environmental problems.

3. The formation of a caring attitude to nature is based on the unity of intellectual, emotional perception of the environment and practical activities to improve it.

4. The process of forming the ecological culture of young people is based on the principles of systematization, continuity and interdisciplinary nature of the content and organization of environmental education. Ecology uses a wide range of research methods. Ecological research methods are methods and means of studying environmental phenomena, divided into field and laboratory. Field methods include the study of environmental phenomena in the natural environment. They help to establish the relationship between organisms, species and communities with the environment, to determine the general picture of the development and vital activity of biosystems. Field methods, in turn, are divided into:

route (direct observation, assessment of the state, measurement, description, drawing up diagrams, maps);

stationary (long-term observation of objects, measurements, description, instrumental reporting);

descriptive (initial acquaintance with the object, direct observation, mapping, inventory, used to register the main characteristics of the objects under study);

experimental (experimentation, testing, quantitative assessment, chemical analysis methods, etc.), monitoring (observation, assessment and forecasting of the state of the natural environment). Laboratory methods are used when performing work in laboratory conditions, but are compatible with field research methods. In ecology, special attention is paid to the modeling method. Modeling is an indirect practical and theoretical method of studying the object, when not the object of interest itself is directly studied, but an auxiliary, artificial or natural system (model) that corresponds to the characteristics of the real object is studied. Any model is

always simplified and reflects the general essence of the process. Environmental monitoring is a comprehensive system of monitoring the state of the environment, assessing and forecasting changes in the state of the environment under the influence of natural and anthropogenic factors. The monitoring process has the following goals: quantitative and qualitative assessment of the state of air, surface water, soil cover, flora and fauna, as well as continuous monitoring of wastewater and waste at industrial enterprises; forecasting the state of the environment and its possible changes; monitoring the physical, chemical and biological processes occurring in the natural environment, the level of pollution of atmospheric air, soil and water bodies and the consequences of its impact on the flora and fauna; providing interested organizations and the public with relevant and timely information about changes in the natural environment, as well as preventing and forecasting its state.

It is also important to pay attention to a number of questionnaires and comparative studies in order to comprehensively cover the problem and determine its solution. In this regard, the results of the social survey allow us to create the following hierarchy of popular environmental practices. When answering the question about the most popular and supported practices in terms of their greatest effectiveness and accessibility, respondents, first of all, gave preference to waste sorting (42.53%), the rejection of harmful household chemicals (36.12%) and plastic (31.96%), water saving (32.31%), safe packaging (31.96%), participation in cleaning days (30.64%) and waste paper collection (29.16%). The option "participation in environmental activities" is presented by almost 21 percent of respondents. On the one hand, this confirms the truth of the picture of youth activity on environmental issues, since it almost coincides with the results of the answers to another question in the questionnaire - 41 "Do you participate in various environmental events and activities?", which was answered positively by 19.1% of respondents. On the other hand, the lower indicators of choosing this generally formulated option, in our opinion, indicate that young people tend to choose specific options for action when it comes to the effectiveness of actions [2012. 40-41]. Naturally, it is advisable to study the experience of different countries, especially developed ones, within the framework of the topic.

- **I. Experience of Uzbekistan:** The Republic of Uzbekistan is implementing a number of measures to improve environmental culture:

- "Green Space" initiative: this project is carrying out tree planting and landscaping work throughout the country.

- Ecological legislation: Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On improving the system of state governance in the field of ecology and environmental protection" No. PF-5024 dated April 21, 2017. Resolution of the

Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the Regulation on the State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan for Ecology and Environmental Protection" No. 29 dated January 15, 2019 - Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to improve the system of state governance in the field of ecology and environmental protection" No. PP-3956 dated October 3, 2018. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-76 dated December 30, 2021 "On measures to organize the activities of state bodies in the field of environmental protection and environmental control". Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-81 dated May 31, 2023 "On measures to transform the sphere of ecology and environmental protection and organize the activities of the authorized state body". Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-171 dated May 31, 2023 "On measures to effectively organize the activities of the Ministry of Ecology, Environmental Protection and Climate Change". The Law "On Environmental Protection", adopted in 2019, created an important legal basis for the development of ecological culture. Article 50 of our Basic Law states that "Citizens are obliged to treat the environment with care." This, in turn, requires citizens to rationally use land, water, forest, underground resources, fauna, flora and other natural resources, to restore and protect them, and to fulfill this obligation in a timely manner. Articles 54, 55 and 100 of our general encyclopedia reflect the issues of environmental protection and rational use of natural resources for legal entities and individuals. Only Article 54 regulates the powers of the owner, which determines the content of property rights in relation to natural resources, and it is confirmed that such economic and production activities do not harm the natural environment. The foundations of the state environmental policy are reflected in Article 55, according to which it is established that land, underground resources, water, flora and fauna and other natural resources are national wealth, they must be used wisely, and they are under state protection [2023.90]. On the basis of these constitutional norms, more than thirty laws and about three hundred by-laws were adopted in the field of ecology, environmental protection and rational use of natural resources. More than ten international documents have been ratified.

- **Ecological education:** In Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to environmental science in schools and universities, and the topic of ecological culture is included in the curriculum.

II. World experience

The experience of countries around the world in developing ecological culture can serve as an example for Uzbekistan:

- Scandinavian countries (Sweden, Norway, Denmark): these countries are distinguished by a high level of environmental awareness of the population and sustainable development policies. They pay great attention to combining state policy, technology and education to improve ecological culture.

- Japan and Germany: these countries have demonstrated practical results in developing ecological culture through innovative technologies and efficient use of resources.

- China: is distinguished by large-scale social campaigns and decisive government measures to raise the population's environmental awareness.

World experience shows that sustainable development policies, education and technological innovations must be combined to form a successful ecological culture.

Criteria for improving ecological culture (Criteria). The success of improving ecological culture is ensured by determining criteria that serve to assess and develop it. These criteria require an interrelated and consistent approach to raising the environmental awareness of different layers of society:

- Education and upbringing; One of the most important criteria of ecological culture is education and upbringing. It is based on understanding the essence of environmental problems and a sense of personal responsibility.

- Environmental education and upbringing: special subjects should be introduced in schools and higher education institutions to form environmental awareness. In Uzbekistan, this process is being implemented by integrating ecology into the general education system.

- Formation of moral values: instilling a sense of care for the environment and a responsible attitude from childhood. For example, in Uzbekistan, within the framework of family values, there are traditions of teaching children to love nature and protect it.

Legal and economic mechanisms: Political and economic mechanisms of the state play an important role in increasing environmental culture.

- *Environmental legislation:* a strong legislative framework guarantees the implementation of effective measures to protect the environment. The environmental laws adopted in Uzbekistan, including the Law "On Environmental Protection", are an important factor in this regard. In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-81 dated May 31, 2023 "On measures to transform the sphere of ecology and environmental protection and organize the activities of the authorized state body", a number of tasks have been set.

- Providing the population with clean drinking water is also an extremely urgent issue for our country. The Resolution of our President dated November 30, 2018 "On additional measures to develop drinking water supply and sewage systems

in the Republic of Uzbekistan" is an important guideline in implementing urgent tasks in this regard.

- Economic incentives: support eco-innovation through tax breaks and subsidies to the public and private sectors during the transition to a green economy.

Technological development and innovation: Technological innovations create new opportunities for improving environmental culture:

- Environmentally friendly technologies: the use of waste-free technologies in production, the use of renewable energy sources. For example, projects on the use of solar and wind energy are developing rapidly in Uzbekistan.

- Information technologies: organizing campaigns to raise the environmental awareness of the population through digital platforms.

Public activity and participation: The direct participation of the population is crucial in the formation of environmental culture:

- Involving local communities in environmental projects.
- Encouraging the population to participate in voluntary environmental actions and events.

A). Principles of improving environmental culture (Principles)

For the process of improving environmental culture to be effective, it is necessary to adhere to scientifically based principles. These principles are aimed at forming environmental awareness and responsibility in society, and each of them has its own characteristics and significance.

B). Sustainability Principle

Sustainable development is based on the principle of protecting the environment and maintaining a balance between human activities. This principle forms the main foundation for improving environmental culture. As emphasized in the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, environmental culture must be integrated into all spheres of society [United Nations, 2015]. In Uzbekistan, this principle is being implemented within the framework of the "Green Economy" strategy. This strategy aims to support economic growth while protecting the environment [Mirziyoyev, 2019].

C). Active Participation Principle

In the process of improving environmental culture, it is necessary to involve all segments of society in active participation.

- Local communities play an important role in solving environmental problems [Smith, 2020].

- In Uzbekistan, this principle is being implemented by organizing environmental projects in neighborhoods and involving the population in campaigns such as "Green Space"[Rasulov, 2021].

This principle is reflected in finding solutions to social responsibility and environmental problems through public participation.

D). **Innovation Principle** Technological innovations are an important means of increasing environmental culture.

- The introduction of environmentally friendly technologies can reduce waste in production and develop the use of renewable energy sources [OECD, 2019].
- Environmental education programs are being introduced in Uzbekistan using digital technologies. For example, online courses and environmental campaigns on social networks are accelerating this process [Karimov, 2020].

E). **International Cooperation Principle** International exchange of experience in developing environmental culture is important.

- The UN and other international organizations emphasize strengthening cooperation between countries in combating environmental problems [UNESCO, 2017].
- Uzbekistan actively participates in international environmental forums and exchanges experience in developing an ecological culture. For example, cooperation projects on "green energy" are being implemented with China [Abdullayev, 2021].

F). **Education and Awareness Principle.** One of the foundations of improving ecological culture is to convey ecological knowledge to the population.

- Ecological education should be carried out not only in educational institutions, but also throughout society [Leopold, 1949].
- State programs and media campaigns are being organized in Uzbekistan to improve ecological knowledge. Through this process, the level of ecological awareness of the population is increasing [Rasulov, 2021]. The implementation of these principles is necessary to improve ecological culture, and their interdependence encourages each member of society to approach environmental issues responsibly.

Practical Recommendations

To successfully improve ecological culture in society, it is necessary to develop specific measures to implement theoretical principles and criteria. The following recommendations are proposed taking into account the conditions of Uzbekistan:

- Reforms in the education system: The development of ecological culture will be effective through its deep integration into the education system.
- Incorporating ecology into school curricula: starting from primary education, the formation of values of environmental responsibility and nature conservation. This process should be based on international experience [UNESCO, 2017].
- Organizing special courses in higher education: special training modules on ecological culture and sustainable development should be developed in all specialties [Karimov, 2020].

-- Creating environmental awareness in society: To develop ecological culture in society, it is necessary to carry out comprehensive information and advocacy campaigns:

- Social media campaigns: publishing informative videos, infographics and useful tips on environmental issues. This approach is especially effective among young people [Smith, 2020].

- Organizing environmental campaigns and events: ensuring direct participation of the population through tree planting events, waste sorting campaigns. For example, the "Green Space" project in Uzbekistan serves as a successful experiment [Rasulov, 2021].

- Public-private sector cooperation

Cooperation between the public and private sectors is important in developing an ecological culture:

- Supporting the transition to a "green economy": it is necessary to develop economic incentive mechanisms for the private sector to introduce ecological technologies [OECD, 2019].

- Supporting ecological innovations: state financing of startups and innovative projects through grants and subsidies can lead to significant progress in the development of ecological culture [Abdullayev, 2021].

--Increasing the activity of local communities: Ensuring the direct participation of the population in solving environmental issues at the local level:

- Supporting voluntary environmental organizations: organizing local environmental groups and allocating resources to them.

- Increasing the "voice of citizens" in solving environmental problems: increasing responsibility and attention to the issue by expanding the participation of the population in the environmental decision-making process [Leopold, 1949].

Technological approach and innovation: The use of digital technologies accelerates the process of increasing environmental culture:

- The mobile applications and online platforms: Development of applications that provide advice on waste recycling, water and energy conservation.

- Artificial intelligence and data analysis: Application of advanced technologies to solve environmental issues, for example, introduction of AI programs to predict climate change [Smith, 2021].

Monitoring and evaluation of results: A monitoring system should be created to measure the effectiveness of measures taken to increase environmental culture:

- Statistical data collection: Conducting surveys to assess the level of environmental knowledge and responsibility of the population.

- Analysis of practical results: Assessing the impact of implemented projects on nature and society [Mirziyoyev, 2019].

Practical recommendations identify important stages in integrating environmental culture into public life. By implementing these recommendations, it is possible to contribute to the national and global development of environmental culture.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMENDATIONS

Ecological culture is a decisive factor for the sustainable development of modern society and is a necessity for ensuring the balance between man and nature. This article analyzes the criteria and principles for improving ecological culture, and also develops practical recommendations using Uzbek and international experience.

The conducted analysis shows that: Education and upbringing play a key role in the formation of ecological culture. By forming environmental awareness starting from preschool education, it is possible to increase environmental responsibility in all layers of society.

1. Increasing the effectiveness of legal and economic mechanisms: significant progress can be achieved in solving environmental problems through strong legislation and economic incentives.

2. Introducing innovative technologies: technological approaches are important in solving environmental problems.

3. Active participation of the population and international cooperation come to the fore as an integral part of the development of ecological culture.

In the case of Uzbekistan, a number of state initiatives aimed at developing ecological culture, including the "Green Space" project and the introduction of environmental legislation, are yielding positive results. At the same time, international experience shows that an integrated approach based on education, technology and public participation is the key to the success of developing an ecological culture [UNESCO, 2017].

The following research areas will remain relevant in the future: Development of effective models for developing an ecological culture in the conditions of Uzbekistan.

- In-depth study of the impact of technological innovations and digital solutions on ecological culture.

- Development of a scientifically based methodology for assessing environmental awareness in society. By developing an ecological culture, it is possible to make a significant contribution not only to environmental protection, but also to the economic, social and cultural development of society. Uzbekistan's efforts in this regard should be continued in line with world experience.

It should be emphasized that although the ecological culture of a person is a complex of activities that is formed from the interactions and dialectical connections of an individual and society with nature, consisting of dynamically changing knowledge, production technologies, values, beliefs, art, ethics and laws, and at the same time rationally coordinated with the needs of the time and future interests, the process of instilling the vital importance of regulatory and legal acts into the consciousness of the population is also a social phenomenon that requires a specific practical and scientific approach. In addition, the formation of ecological culture is inseparable from social values and economic processes, the natural and geographical environment.

Used literature (References)

1. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, No. PP-300 dated 11.09.2023. September 11, 2023.
2. Karabukaev K.Sh. Ecological culture of society. Theory and practice Bishkek Maxprint 2018. - 230 p.
3. Yazdonov Z.Sh. Trends in the restoration of the traditions of the Uzbek people's ecological culture and the development of the traditions of the natural sciences. Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) dissertation work. Abstract of the thesis. Samarkand – 2019. – P.11.
4. Abstract of the thesis. Samarkand – 2019. – P.12.
5. Nigmatov A.I. Ecology: an explanatory dictionary of basic terms and expressions. - T., 2002, pp. 15-16.
6. Environmental problems and the role of journalism in solving them
7. ECOLOGICAL CULTURE OF SCHOOL STUDENTS Svetlana Yurevna Lanina. Environmental culture of schoolchildren. Candidate of physics and mathematics, associate professor, Blagoveshchensk State Pedagogical University, Blagoveshchensk. Ученые записки университета имени П.Ф. Лесгафта. – 2022. – № 8 (210).
8. Marar O.I. Ecological culture in contemporary Russian society: autoref. dis. ... PhD sociologist. science Moscow, 2012. 41 p.
9. Marar O.I. Ecological culture in contemporary Russian society: current problems. M.: Izd-vo MNEPU. 2011. 226 p. 32
10. Rybakova M.V. Sotsialnye ekologicheskie praktiki: sostoyanie i mekhaniznyi upravleniya. M.: KDU. 2012. 318 p. ;
11. Tursunov H.T., Rakhimova T.U. Ecology. Study guide. Tashkent., 2006.
12. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. -Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2023. - 80 p
13. Leopold, A. (1949). A Sand County Almanac. Oxford University Press.

14. OECD. (2019). Green Growth Indicators. Paris: OECD Publishing.
15. Rasulov, D. (2021). Ecological culture and youth education. *Ecological Journal of Uzbekistan*, 34(2), 45–52.
16. United Nations. (2015). Transforming our world: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. Retrieved from <https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/>
17. Smith, J. (2021). Community Participation in Sustainable Development. *Journal of Environmental Studies*, 48(3), 321–334.
18. UNESCO. (2017). Education for Sustainable Development Goals: Learning Objectives. Paris: UNESCO Publishing.
19. Karimov, B. (2020). Enhancing Environmental Culture through Digital Technologies. *Scientific Journal of Information Technologies*, 12(4), 27–35.
20. Abdullayev, M. (2021). International Environmental Projects and Uzbekistan’s Participation. *Journal of Central Asian Studies*, 19(1), 12–20.
21. Mirziyoyev, S. M. (2019). Strategy for Transition to a Green Economy: A Path to Sustainable Development. Tashkent: Uzbekistan State Publishing House.
22. World Bank. (2020). Investing in Green Growth for a Sustainable Future. Washington, DC: World Bank Publications.